

Corrigendum to

“Effects of resolution on the relative importance of numerical and physical horizontal diffusion in atmospheric composition modelling” published in Atmos. Chem. Phys., 10, 2737–2743, doi:10.5194/acp-10-2737-2010, 2010

M. D’Isidoro, A. Maurizi, and F. Tampieri

CNR-ISAC, via Gobetti 101, 40129 Bologna, Italy

Unfortunately, a typing error was noticed in the acknowledgements to the online publication and the final version should be as follows:

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Correspondence to: M. D’Isidoro
(m.disidoro@isac.cnr.it)